

Polymerization of Acrylamide by Permanganate/Bisulphite Redox Pair and Role of Organic Solvents as Retarders

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Kinetics of aqueous polymerization of acrylamide with KMnO_4 /sodium metabisulphite redox pair were studied at 35° under atmospheric oxygen. The rate of polymerization was found dependent on first power of the monomer and catalyst while half power of the activator concentration. The energy of activation has been found to be $10.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ between 25 and 45° . The effect of various additives on the course of polymerization was studied qualitatively. The retarding effect of organic solvents has been studied quantitatively and retardation constants have been calculated using newly developed 'Intercept method'.

Although potassium permanganate forms an efficient redox systems¹ with a variety of reducing agents such as glucose², aminoacids³ and glyceric acid⁴ under an inert atmosphere, yet its use as a redox component in oxygen atmosphere is less reported. In the present study sodium metabisulphite has been coupled with potassium permanganate to form a new redox couple for the polymerization of a acrylamide under atmospheric oxygen.

Results and Discussion

A plausible mechanism for the polymerization of acrylamide initiated by potassium permanganate/metabisulphite has been proposed as follows.

The distinguishing feature of the permanganate containing systems is that there are two consecutive redox systems operate in the presence of monomer⁵, viz. permanganate (oxidant) and monomer (reductant), and separated manganese dioxide (oxidant) and the added reducing agent (activator). Thus, permanganate first reacts with acrylamide to produce manganese dioxide which under acidic condition reacts with bisulphite ions to generate free radicals (R) and reactive Mn^{3+} ions which further participate in radical generation steps,

The free radicals so produced initiate the polymerization.

Propagation :

and so on

Termination :

The termination of growing macroradical chain (RM_n^{\cdot}) has been supposed to be of unimolecular in mode. In a unimolecular termination a single macroradical chain is deactivated to a dead polymer molecule by the impurities or dissolved metal ions (Mn^{3+} Mn^{4+}) present in the system⁶. Such a linear termination always confirms a first power dependence of rate on catalyst concentration.

Rate expression: The rate expression may be derived by determining the concentrations of free radicals by applying steady state assumption,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} [\text{R}^{\cdot}] &= k_1 [\text{HSO}_3^-] [\text{Mn}^{4+}] + k_2 [\text{HSO}_3^-] \\ &\quad - k_1 [\text{R}^{\cdot}] [\text{M}] = 0 \\ \text{or } [\text{R}^{\cdot}] &= \frac{[\text{HSO}_3^-] \{k_1 [\text{Mn}^{4+}] + k_2 [\text{Mn}^{3+}]\}}{k_1 [\text{M}]} \quad (7) \end{aligned}$$

On applying steady state to $[\text{Mn}^{3+}]$ ions, and substituting its value in equation (7),

$$[\text{R}^{\cdot}] = \frac{2k_1 [\text{HSO}_3^-] [\text{Mn}^{4+}]}{k_1 [\text{M}]} \quad (8)$$

Now at steady state, $R_i = R_t$

$$\text{or } k_1 [\text{R}^{\cdot}] [\text{M}] = k_t [\text{RM}_n^{\cdot}]$$

$$\text{or } [\text{RM}_n^{\cdot}] = \frac{k_1}{k_t} [\text{R}^{\cdot}] [\text{M}]$$

$$\text{or } [\text{RM}_n^{\cdot}] = \frac{2k_1}{k_t} [\text{HSO}_3^-] [\text{Mn}^{4+}] \quad (9)$$

The rate of polymerization

$$R_p = k_p [\text{M}] [\text{RM}_n^{\cdot}]$$

Therefore, from equation (9) we have

$$R_p = \left(\frac{k_1 k_p}{k_t} \right) [\text{M}] [\text{HSO}_3^-] [\text{Mn}^{4+}] \quad (10)$$

Now from equation (1), we get

$$k[S_2O_5^{2-}][H_2O] = k'[HSO_3^-]^2$$

$$\text{or } [HSO_3^-] = \left(\frac{k}{k'}\right)^{0.5} [S_2O_5^{2-}]^{0.5} \quad (11)$$

Now from equations (10) and (11) we get

$$R_p = \left(\frac{2k_1k_p}{k_t}\right) \left(\frac{k}{k'}\right)^{0.5} [M][S_2O_5^{2-}]^{0.5} [Mn^{4+}] \quad (12)$$

$$\text{or } R_p \propto [M]^{1.0} [\text{Bisulphite}]_{0.5} [KMnO_4]^{1.0}$$

The derived rate expression is in agreement with the experimental results except that the 0.82 power on the bisulphite concentration of experimental results is quite higher than the derived 0.5 power. The deviation observed has been explained later in the text.

Role of atmospheric oxygen: In vinyl polymerization the role of oxygen as a retarder or inhibitor is well known. Most polymerization reactions are commonly carried out in an inert atmosphere to meet out the problem of retardation by atmospheric oxygen. But, there are several redox systems^{7,8} known where the oxygen accelerates the polymerization by acting as a cocatalyst. The well studied example being the ascorbic acid containing redox systems where oxygen facilitates the possibility of ascorbic acid undergoing autoxidation like other hydroxyketones of enediols⁹ and thus participates in the reaction. The catalysing action of molecular oxygen with autoxidisable substrates like hydrazine hydrate¹⁰ and sulphite ion¹¹ in different systems of catalysed polymerization of vinyl monomers has also been observed by others.

In the present system, the catalytic activity of atmospheric oxygen may be attributed to the oxidation of bisulphite ion⁵ giving rise to the formation of sulphite radicals,

The catalysing role of oxygen was also confirmed by carrying out experiment in nitrogen atmosphere where comparatively lower yield of polymer was obtained. The lower yield of polymer also suggests that reaction (13) is not only the reaction generating free radicals in the reaction medium.

Monomer dependence: The initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion are found to increase with the increase in concentration of monomer in the range $5.0-20.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³. On increasing the concentration of the monomer, the availability of monomer molecules in the propagation step increases which results in an increase in the initial rate and as well as in limiting conversion. The rate of polymerization has been found to be of first power dependence on monomer

concentration as obtained from double logarithmic plot (not shown).

Redox component dependence: The initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion are found to increase on increasing the concentrations of the activator (bisulphite) and the catalyst (permanganate) in the range of $0.52-2.52 \times 10^{-2}$ and $1.21-5.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ respectively.

On increasing the concentration of the activator, greater number of the radicals are generated from equations (2) and (3), which will result in an increased rate of polymerization and limiting conversion. From the double logarithmic plot (not shown) the activator exponent has been found to be 0.82 which is higher than that given by the rate expression. The deviation so observed may be explained by the fact that bisulphite may undergo some side-reactions of the type,

When the concentration of catalyst is increased, the concentration of [Mn⁴⁺] ion increases which in turn increases the concentration of free radicals (R[•]) as shown by equations (2) and (3). The initial rate of polymerization as well as limiting conversion increase with the increase in concentration of primary free radicals (R[•]) responsible for initiating polymerization of acrylamide. A first power dependence of rate of polymerization on catalyst concentration has been obtained from the double logarithmic plot, which supports the unimolecular termination. Termination by the dissolved metal ions Mn⁴⁺/Mn³⁺ also may not be ruled out. Our results find support from similar type of work reported elsewhere¹².

Temperature dependence: When temperature of the reaction medium is increased from 25 to 35°, the initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion increase, and beyond 35° a fall in the initial rate and limiting conversion is observed. The observed increase is due to the fact that with increase in temperature the rate of active centre formation increases which consequently increases the initial rate and limiting conversion. On increasing the temperature further (beyond 35°), some side-reactions may start which may cause an increase in the rate of primary radical termination thus decreasing the initial rate and limiting conversion. The overall energy of activation as calculated from the Arrhenius plot (not shown) has been found to 10.5 kcal mol⁻¹, which is in good agreement with the values reported for similar type of redox systems¹².

H⁺ ion dependence: As the permanganate initiated systems are quite sensitive to H⁺ ion concentration, the effect of H⁺ ion on the course of polymerization has been studied by the addition

of sulphuric acid in the range $4.7-6.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} . It was observed that when the concentration of H^+ ions was kept below 4.7×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} no polymerization could take place as the precipitated manganese dioxide could not be dissolved by the insufficient amount of acid present. As the concentration of H^+ ions is varied in the range $4.7-5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , both the initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion increase. The increase observed is well explained as the function of H^+ ions is to dissolve separated MnO_2 and yield Mn^{4+} ions which are responsible for the radical generation step (equation 2). Obviously an increase in H^+ ion concentration will result in an increase in the rate of formation of primary free radicals which in turn, will enhance the efficiency of the redox system. But on increasing the concentration of H^+ ion beyond 5.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} , a decrease in the initial rate and limiting conversion is observed which may be due to the reduction of Mn^{4+} ions,

It is therefore clear that Mn^{4+} ions, which are mainly responsible for the radical generation step (equation 2), are directly changed into Mn^{2+} ions without generating free radicals or reactive Mn^{3+} ions. Also, at higher concentration of sulphuric acid, the sulphate ions cause interference with the normal polymerization process by forming complex with Mn^{3+} ions. The complex formed is believed²³ to be $[\text{Mn}(\text{SO}_4)_2]^-$. Upon further increasing the concentration of H^+ ions beyond 6.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} no polymerization was observed.

Effect of inorganic salts and complexing agents: The effect of cations and anions on the course of polymerization has been studied by the addition of inorganic salts such as sulphates of alkali metals and potassium halides to the reaction medium in equimolar amounts. The initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion were found to decrease in both the case (Fig. 1).

In case of effect of cations, the increasing order of depression or initial rate is $\text{K}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{Li}^+$. While in case of the anions, the increasing order of depression is $\text{Cl}^- < \text{Br}^- < \text{I}^-$.

The depression of initial rate and limiting conversion may be due to the increased ionic strength of the medium. The ionic dissociation of the added electrolyte also interferes with the normal polymerization procedure and results in a premature termination of the growing polymer chains. A large reduction in the activity of the $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ ions occurs due to the coupling of these ions with the added salt.

The addition of complexing agents like NaF and EDTA causes depression in the initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion. The depression caused by NaF may be due to the

Fig. 1. Effect of inorganic salts on the plot of initial course of polymerization of acrylamide for varying concentrations of various salts added at fixed $[\text{M}] = 10.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{KMnO}_4] = 5.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{Bisulphite}] = 2.52 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[\text{H}^+] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm^{-3} , temp. = $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$: (●) $\text{Li}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , (□) $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , (■) $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , (⊗) $\text{KCl} = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , (△) $\text{KBr} = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} , (○) $\text{KI} = 0.01$ mol dm^{-3} and (○) no salt added.

complex formed of the type MnF_4^- between Mn^{3+} and fluoride ions. Thus Mn^{3+} ions are prevented from participating in the radical generation step (equation 3) and thus depression in the polymerization rate is observed. Similar type of results were obtained earlier¹⁴. In the case of EDTA, which is more powerful complexing agent than NaF, the formation of a non-radical ion and stable chelate with Mn^{3+} ions occurs which therefore results in the depression in a initial rate of polymerization and limiting conversion as well, by inhibiting Mn^{3+} ion to take part actively in radical generation process (equation 3).

Effect of surfactants: The addition of cationic and anionic surface active agents like cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium oleate respectively, reduce the initial rate and limiting conversion when added to the reaction medium at below and above their CMC values (Fig. 2). The depression caused by sodium oleate may be explained due to the formation of a specific ion-pair binding of the cations $\text{Mn}^{4+}/\text{Mn}^{3+}$ with the anionic end and thus lowering the rate of primary radical generation. In case of the cationic surfactant (CTAB), ion-pair binding of large MnO_2 ions with the large cation R_4N^+ lower the rate of primary radical generation. Friend and Alexander¹⁸ reported such ion-pair binding above the CMC only. Our result find support from our previous work³.

Fig. 2. Effect of surfactants on the plot of initial course of polymerization of acrylamide for varying concentrations of surfactants at fixed $[M]=10.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KMnO}_4]=5.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Bisulphite}]=2.52 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+]=5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. $=35 \pm 0.2^\circ$: (\blacktriangle) sodium oleate $=0.01 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) sodium oleate $=0.05 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (Δ) sodium oleate $=0.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\square) CTAB $=0.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\bullet) CTAB $=0.82 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, (\blacksquare) CTAB $=1.64 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and (\circ) no surfactant added.

Fig. 3. Effect of various organic solvents (5%, v/v) on the plot of initial course of polymerization of acrylamide at fixed $[M]=10.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{KMnO}_4]=5.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Bisulphite}]=2.52 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+]=5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. $=35 \pm 0.2^\circ$: (\bullet) i-PrOH, (\blacktriangle) t-BuOH, (\circ) benzene, (Δ) MeOH, (\square) EtOH, (\blacksquare) DMF, (\diamond) nitrobenzene, (\otimes) DMSO and (\odot) H_2O medium (no additive).

Effect of organic solvents: Since the properties of a polymer mostly depend on the nature of the medium, various organic solvents such as methanol, ethanol, iso-propanol, t-butanol, DMF, DMSO, benzene and nitrobenzene have been studied to observe their effect on the course of polymerization. When added to the reaction medium in equal volume (5%, v/v) a depression in the initial rate of polymerization and the limiting conversion has been observed (Fig. 3). The increasing order of depression by these solvents is i-PrOH < t-BuOH < benzene < MeOH < EtOH < DMF < nitrobenzene < DMSO. The cause of depression in the initial rate of polymerization and the limiting conversion by the added organic solvents may be explained as follows. (i) When the organic solvents are added to the reaction medium, they cause a decrease in the area of shielding of a strong hydration layer in aqueous medium which results in the termination of radical end of the growing chain. (ii) Some amount of catalyst may be consumed in the oxidation of these organic solvents due to which the concentration of catalyst decreases and a depression in initial rate is observed. The sluggish radicals thus produced may not be equally capable of initiating the polymerization.

The retardation by these organic solvents has been studied quantitatively and the numerical values of the retardation constants have been calculated using a new technique¹². In the redox

initiated polymerization retarded by a retarder (Z), the following mechanism may be given,

Based on the above mechanism, the following rate expression has been developed for the evaluation of retardation constant,

$$[\text{M}] = I \left(\frac{[\text{Z}_0]}{x-x'} \right) - I \left(\frac{Kt}{x-x'} \right)$$

where $I = K_z/k_p$, the retardation constant for retarder Z, Z_0 is the initial concentration of retarder Z, $x' = d[\text{M}]_{\text{retd.}}/dt$, i.e. rate of change of monomer concentration under retarded condition, $x = d[\text{M}]/dt$, i.e. rate of change of monomer concentration under unretarded condition and K is a constant.

It is very clear from the equation that a plot of [monomer] vs time (t) will give a straight line (Fig. 4) and from intercept of the line drawn the value of retardation constant (I) may be calculated. The method has been named as 'Intercept method'

Fig. 4. $[M]$ vs t curves for various organic solvents as retarders in acrylamide polymerization at $35 \pm 0.2^\circ$, when added in equal volume (5%, v/v) of (□) *i*-PrOH, (●) *t*-BuOH, (⊙) benzene, (⊖) MeOH, (⊕) DMF and (△) nitrobenzene.

and has been well described in our earlier communication¹². The values of retardation constant are summarised in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF RETARDATION CONSTANT

Solvent	k_s/k_p
<i>i</i> -PrOH	0.002 5
<i>t</i> -BuOH	0.004 3
Benzene	0.023 3
MeOH	0.001 9
DMF	0.232 2
Nitrobenzene	2.456 0

Experimental

Acrylamide was recrystallised from methanol (A.R.) and dried under reduced pressure.

Potassium permanganate and sodium metabisulphite (AnalaR) were used. Fresh solutions in double-distilled water were prepared for each run.

The apparatus employed and the polymerization procedure were similar to those adopted in our earlier communications^{3,16}. The rate of polymerization was followed by estimating the consumption of double bonds of acrylamide¹⁷. While studying the effect of retarders like benzene and nitrobenzene, the kinetic course of polymerization was followed gravimetrically by precipitating the polymer formed in acetone medium, as the two solvents produced a heterogeneity in the reaction medium under the existing experimental conditions.

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